

WHAT PISA MAY TELL US ABOUT MATHEMATICAL LITERACY IN AN ERA OF DATA SCIENCE

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The demands of mathematical literacy are responsive to the context in which they are used. For many decades, this context has remained largely stable, especially for classroom mathematical practices. Increasingly, changes in science and engineering have begun to redefine mathematical literacy – changes that are most evident in the emerging field of data science. This paper reviews emerging definitions of data science, and their implications for the workplace and scientific research and development. It will use a report on Junior Cycle Project Maths (viewed through the lens of PISA 2016) as an approximate indicator of where Irish students stand on certain elements of data science.

PISA AND TOPICS FOR MATHEMATICS LITERACY

For the purposes of international comparison by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OCED), mathematical literacy was defined alongside mathematics, with the latter, not surprisingly, as the centre of gravity of the construct (OECD, 2006, p.12):

an individual's capacity to identify and understand the role that mathematics plays in the world, to make well-founded judgments and to use and engage with mathematics in ways that meet the needs of that individual's life as a constructive, concerned and reflective citizen.

At the same time, the definition recognised that the construct of “mathematical literacy” must extend beyond mathematics and be responsive to changes in the world and in individuals' lives (OECD 2006, p. 76):

A mathematically literate citizen realises how quickly change is taking place and the consequent need to be open to lifelong learning. Adapting to these changes in a creative, flexible and practical way is a necessary condition for successful citizenship. The skills learned at school will probably not be sufficient to serve the needs of citizens for the majority of their adult life.

Even back in 2006, the OCED recognized that changes in technology and the needs of the workplace would place new demands on how “mathematical literacy” would be defined and enacted (OECD, 2006, p. 76):

The requirements for competent and reflective citizenship also affect the workforce. Workers are less and less expected to carry out repetitive physical chores. Instead, they are engaged actively in monitoring output from a variety of high-technology machines, dealing with a flood of information and engaging in team problem solving. The trend is that more and more occupations will require the ability to understand, communicate, use and explain concepts and procedures based on mathematical thinking. The steps of the mathematisation process are the building blocks of this kind of mathematical thinking.

The OECD has also defined the context for mathematical literacy as including four domains: (a) personal, (b) occupational, (c) societal and (d) scientific (OECD, 2017, pp. 61-62).

A more recent definition of mathematical literacy in PISA defines it as including “[reason] mathematically and [use] mathematical concepts, procedures, facts and tools to describe, explain and predict phenomena” (OECD, 2017, p. 51). In other words, the OECD has recognised the growing value of statistics, science and engineering ideas for the construct of “mathematical literacy.”

PISA CORE TOPICS

Those designing PISA framed the core concepts needed for mathematics literacy (OECD, 2006, p. 82), which remain up to PISA 2018 as: (1) space and shape, (2) change and relationships, (3) quantity, and (4) uncertainty.

Under the topic of space and shape, OECD (2006) emphasised (p. 84):

- Recognising shapes and patterns
- Describing, encoding and decoding visual information
- Understanding dynamic changes to shapes
- Similarities and differences
- Relative positions
- 2-D and 3-D representations and the relations between them
- Navigation through space

For change and relationship, the OECD (2006, p. 86) noted that:

Change and relationships can be represented in a variety of ways including numerical (for example in a table), symbolical, graphical, algebraic and geometrical. Translation between these representations is of key importance, as is the recognition of an understanding of fundamental relationships and types of change. Students should be aware of the concepts of linear growth (additive process), exponential growth (multiplicative process) and periodic growth, as well as logistic growth, at least informally as a special case of exponential growth.

The OECD (2017, p. 59) added:

Change and relationships is evident in such diverse settings as growth of organisms, music, and the cycle of seasons, weather patterns, employment levels, and economic conditions. Aspects of the traditional mathematical content of functions and algebra, including algebraic expressions, equations and inequalities, and tabular and graphical representations, are central in describing, modelling, and interpreting change phenomena.

For quantity, OECD (2006, p. 89) explained that:

Important aspects of quantity include an understanding of relative size, the recognition of numerical patterns, and the use of numbers to represent quantities and quantifiable attributes of real-world objects (counts and measures). Furthermore, quantity deals with the processing and understanding of numbers that are represented to us in various ways. An important aspect of dealing with quantity is quantitative reasoning. Essential components of quantitative reasoning are number sense, representing numbers in various ways, understanding the meaning of operations, having a feel for the magnitude of numbers, mathematically elegant computations, mental arithmetic and estimating.

The OCED (2017, p. 59) added:

To engage with the quantification of the world involves understanding measurements, counts, magnitudes, units, indicators, relative size, and numerical trends and patterns. Aspects of quantitative reasoning—such as number sense, multiple representations of numbers, elegance in computation, mental calculation, estimation and assessment of reasonableness of results—are the essence of mathematical literacy relative to quantity . . . Geometry serves as an essential foundation for space and shape, but the category extends beyond traditional geometry in content, meaning, and method, drawing on elements of other mathematical areas such as spatial visualisation, measurement and algebra.

And, for uncertainty, OECD (2006, p. 93) viewed the topic as overlapping significantly with statistics.

- The omnipresence of variation in processes
- The need for data about processes
- The design of data production with variation in mind
- The quantification of variation
- The explanation of variation

To this topic, the OCED (2017, p. 60) added: “The uncertainty and data content category includes recognising the place of variation in processes, having a sense of the quantification of that variation, acknowledging uncertainty and error in measurement, and knowing about chance.”

Shiel and Kelleher (2017), who analysed the PISA 2012 data under the four headings of (1) space and shape, (2) change and relationships, (3) quantity, and (4) uncertainty reported the following findings:

Space and shape (geometry and trigonometry)

A consistent finding in PISA mathematics has been the low performance of students in Ireland on Space & Shape items. In the two cycles in which mathematics has been a major assessment domain in PISA (2003, 2012), students in Ireland have achieved mean scores below the corresponding OECD average scores on Space & Shape, with female students, in particular, struggling on items in this content area. (Shiel & Kelleher, 2017, p. 151)

Change and relationships (algebra)

In PISA 2012, students in Ireland achieved a mean score on Change & Relationships (501.1) that was significantly higher than the corresponding OECD average (492.5), though Ireland lagged behind a number of countries including Canada (525), Belgium (513), and Switzerland (530) as well as Japan (542) and Korea (559) ...

Functions. ...the Functions content area is integrated into Change & Relationships in the PISA assessment, and into Algebra in TIMSS. Hence, international assessments do not provide separate information on how students perform in this area. (Shiel & Kelleher, 2017, p. 152-153).

Quantity (number)

In PISA 2012, students in Ireland achieved a mean score on Quantity that was significantly above the corresponding OECD average (by 10.1 score points), though students in Ireland at the 90th percentile achieved a score that was not significantly different from the OECD average at that marker (Shiel & Kelleher, 2017, p. 149).

Uncertainty and data (statistics and probability)

Students in Ireland perform relatively well in the corresponding area in PISA mathematics (Uncertainty & Data), with mean scores that were significantly above the corresponding OECD averages in 2003 and 2012. Indeed, Uncertainty & Data was an area of strength for students in Ireland on PISA, even before the implementation of Project Maths, though there was a significant drop of 8.5 score points between 2003 and 2012. Students in Ireland also performed well on Data & Chance in TIMSS 2015, with a mean score that was significantly higher than on average across OECD countries in the study. (Shiel & Kelleher, 2017, p. 149).

ENTER DATA SCIENCE

Do these PISA results provide a basis to assess how well Irish students are prepared to engage a version of mathematical literacy that includes new demands from science, engineering and the changing workplace? Why is this important?

The “flood of information” anticipated by OCED in 2006 has become a tsunami of data due to ubiquitous data-gathering technologies and exponential growth in computational power. Primary among data-gathering technologies is the emergence of the “internet of things.”

The internet of things is the network of devices with sensors that permeate our homes, healthcare, manufacturing, transportation, agriculture, and places of work. According to Forbes magazine, the internet of things has “six core building blocks (hardware, connectivity, cloud platform & analytics, applications, cybersecurity, and system integration) and six supporting technologies (additive manufacturing [3D printing], augmented and virtual reality [AR & VR], collaborative robots, connected machine vision, drones / UAVs, self-driving vehicles [SDVs])” (<https://www.forbes.com/sites/louiscolombus/2018/12/13/2018-roundup-of-internet-of-things-forecasts-and-market-estimates/#a2c5df67d838>).

Data from these devices can inform better use of a myriad of objects, tools and resources, including smart phones, smart homes, smart hospitals, smart manufacturing, smart agriculture, and smart workplaces.

Not surprisingly, this deluge of data is transforming the nature and practice of science and engineering. At the US National Science Foundation, the importance of data science is recognised by connected funding across a set of “big ideas” that will guide billions of dollars of future investment. While each of the big ideas differs in contexts (e.g., navigating the new Arctic, biology, the future of work, or astronomy), it is clear that advances in data and data analytics are the primary drivers (https://www.nsf.gov/news/special_reports/big_ideas/).

Implications for the definition of mathematical literacy

Leading academic institutions are responding to this data challenge by developing an emerging interdisciplinary effort called “data science.” Data science is a combination of inferential thinking (i.e., statistics and mathematics), computational thinking (i.e., elements of computer science), and an identified content or knowledge area of application (Blei & Smyth, 2017; Cao, 2017; Wing, Janeja, Kloefkorn & Erickson, 2018).

Importantly, while data science includes mathematical and statistical foundations, it adds concepts from computer science and emphasises how data are collected, managed, and analysed. In a consensus report of a panel of experts, the US National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine add elements to mathematics and statistics in order for data scientists to develop “data acumen” (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2018, p. 22):

- Computational foundations,
- Data management and curation,
- Data description and visualization,
- Data modeling and assessment,
- Workflow and reproducibility,
- Communication and teamwork,
- Domain-specific considerations, and
- Ethical problem solving.

PISA, PROJECT MATHS AND DATA SCIENCE

Could Ireland’s “Project Maths,” which was tailored in large part to the prior PISA test performance (Kirwan, 2015), provide a basis to teach and assess mathematical literacy if it were extended to more elements of data science?

To partially answer this question, we note that Project Maths was at least partially based on Freudenthal’s realistic mathematics education (RME) (Conway & Sloane, 2005).

Leavy and Sloane (2011a) argued, based on their assessment of preservice primary school teachers’ understanding of statistics, that statistics was mostly understood procedurally, making it difficult for these beginning teachers to conceptualize and engage statistics instruction in real-world contexts. However, Sloane (2005) showed that through the use of intensive Lesson Study, teachers could engage student learning of mathematics that went beyond procedural fluency. Leavy and Sloane (2011b), working with preservice teachers in

Ireland, again showed that, with intensive support, preservice teachers can move beyond procedural applications of statistics.

Based on the analyses by Shiel and Kelleher (2017), Irish students at the Junior Cycle have relatively solid foundations in: (a) change and relationship, (b) quantity, and (c) uncertainty and data. We see from the above analyses that Irish students have a reasonably good preparation in the mathematical and statistical elements posed by PISA. Yet, the framing of mathematical literacy by PISA continues to view mathematics and statistical foundations as mostly stand-alone constructs that are yet to be integrated with computational, data management, and domain-specific considerations (not to mention ethical or privacy concerns).

Especially in the case of uncertainty and data, work by Leavy and Sloane (2011a, 2011b) described the fragility of this inference in the population of pre-service primary school teachers and explored the training efforts needed for such an inference to be real. Extra effort will be required there and in space and shape to round out the mathematics literacy aspects of data science.

LOOKING FORWARD

We acknowledge the limitations of this analysis. First, definitions of data science extend well beyond traditional mathematical topics. Indeed, we limited our analysis to overlap with the mathematical and statistical foundations of data science. We further limited our analysis to those elements of mathematics and statistics that bore resemblance to ideas assessed in the PISA framework. And even here, there is (especially at the Junior Cycle) limited overlap with topics such as (a) set theory and basic logic, (b) multivariate thinking via functions and graphical displays, (c) basic probability theory and randomness, (c) matrices and basic linear algebra, (d) networks and graph theory, and (e) optimization.

Nonetheless, the transformations in science and engineering and the workplace that are already in progress, and the investments in research and development exemplified by the US National Science Foundation, suggest serious attention may be warranted to expanding definitions of mathematical literacy to incorporate data science in Ireland.

REFERENCES

- Blei, D., & Smyth, P. (2017). Science and data science. *Proceedings of the National Academies of Sciences*, 114 (33), 8689-8692.
- Cao, L (2017). Data science: A comprehensive overview. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*. 50(3). Doi: 10.1145/3076253.
- Conway, P. & Sloane, F. (2006). *International trends in post primary mathematics education*. Dublin: National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- Kirwan, L (2015). Mathematics curriculum in Ireland: The influence of PISA on the development of Project Maths. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 2015, 8(2), 317-332.

- Leavy, A. & Sloane, F. (2011a). Understanding and modelling pre-service teacher's knowledge of statistics. In T. Dooley and D. Corcoran (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Third National Conference on research in mathematics education: MEI3*. Dublin: St. Patrick's College of Education.
- Leavy, A. & Sloane, F. (2011b). Applying results of statistics education research to teaching statistics in Irish primary schools. Author: *Proceedings of the World Congress of Statistics (ISI-2011)*. Amsterdam: IOS Press.
- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2018). *Data science for undergraduates: Opportunities and options*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25104>.
- OECD. (2006). *Assessing scientific, reading and mathematical literacy: A framework for PISA 2006*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2016). *PISA 2015 assessment and analytical framework. Science, reading, mathematics and financial literacy*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- OECD (2017). *PISA for development assessment and analytical framework: Reading, mathematics and science*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Shiel, G., & Kelleher, C. (2017). *An evaluation of the impact of Project Maths on the performance of students in Junior Cycle mathematics*. Dublin: Educational Research Centre. Accessed at: http://www.erc.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/PM_EvaluationStrand1.pdf
- Sloane, F. (2005). Lesson study in Japanese mathematics classrooms: An exemplar of design research. In S. Close, T. Dooley and D. Corcoran (Eds.), *Proceedings of the first national conference on research in mathematics education: MEI1*. St. Patrick's College of Education, Dublin: Ireland.
- Wing, J. M., Janeja, V. P., Kloefkorn, T. & Erickson, L. C. (2018). *Data science leadership summit: Summary report*. Technical Report: Columbia University, NY.

